

Digital Value System-The Way to Future

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Abstract - Value can be considered as the sum total of all the changes happening in this world / universe and has been there since life existed in the universe. In this paper we will be trying to explain a unique value system for human kind fulfilling the economic, ethical and social imaginary dimensions of value under one single umbrella of the Digital Value System.

Index Terms – Digital Value System (DVS), Digital Money (DM), Digital Currency (DC), Essentiality Index (EI), Availability Index, Artificial Intelligence (AI)

I. INTRODUCTION

The term value always brings a bunch of ideas to everyone's mind and differs from person to person and on perspectives. Human kind has always been trying to define value in terms of economics, ethics, social imaginary and so on; but never reached its fulfillment as desired. We try to value each and every thing in monetary terms but at the same time there are many factors which are beyond defining; and providing value for the same is near to impossible like for sunlight, gravity etc.

Have you ever wondered why this world ever exists? Why do we live and why do we work for? The conclusion we were able to arrive at was that, it was for change or transformation; and value is something which is created as a result of or part of such transformation or change. So why is it important to think about value?

In this chapter we will be trying to explain a unique value system for human kind fulfilling the economic, ethical and social imaginary dimensions of value under one single umbrella of the Digital Value System.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The earliest and one of the most renowned economic methods for exchange of value was the barter system where value was determined and transferred by exchange of goods and services in return of goods and services.

The barter system was replaced by the fiat currency system forming the most visible and accepted part of the present economic value system. We value goods and services in monetary terms and exchange them using currency (physical or digital) as a transaction medium.

History of Fiat Money

Fiat money originated from China in the 10th century, mainly in the Yuan, Tang, Song, and Ming dynasties. In the Tang Dynasty (618-907), there was a high demand for metallic currency that exceeded the supply of precious metals. The people were familiar with the use of credit notes, and they readily accepted pieces of paper or paper drafts. A shortage of coins forced people to change from coins to notes. During the Song Dynasty (960-1276), there was a booming business in the Sichuan region that led to a shortage of copper money. Traders started issuing private notes covered by a monetary reserve, and it was considered to be the first legal tender. Paper money became the only legal tender in the Yuan Dynasty (1276-1367), and issuing of notes was conferred to the Ministry of Finance during the Ming Dynasty (1368-1644). The West started using paper money in the 18th century. American colonies, France, and the Continental Congress started issuing bills of credit that were used to make payments. The provincial governments issued notes that the holders would use to pay taxes to the authorities. The issuing of too many bills of credit generated some controversy due to the dangers of inflation. In some regions, such as New England and the Carolinas, the bills depreciated significantly and there was a hike in commodity prices as the bills lost value. During wars, countries turn to fiat currencies to preserve the value of precious metals such as gold and silver. For example, the Federal Government of the United States turned to a form of fiat currency referred to as "Greenbacks" during the American Civil War. The government halted the convertibility of its paper money to gold or silver during this war.

In the early 20th century, the government and banks had promised to allow the conversion of notes and coins into their nominal commodity on demand. However, the high cost of the American Civil War and the need to rebuild the economy forced the government to cancel the redemption. The Bretton Woods Agreement fixed the value of one troy ounce of gold to 35 United States Dollars. However, in 1971, United States President, Richard Nixon, introduced a series of economic measures including canceling the direct convertibility of dollars into gold due to declining gold reserves. Since then, most countries have adopted fiat monies that are exchangeable between major currencies. Currently, most nations use paper-based fiat currencies that only serve as a mode of payment.

Fiat currency is not supported by any physical commodity, but by the faith of its holders and virtue of a government declaration. Paper money acts as a storage medium for purchasing power and an alternative to the barter system. It allows people to buy products and services as they need without having to trade product for product, as was the case with barter trade. Due to its ability to store purchasing power, people can make plans with ease and create specialized economic activities. For example, a business dealing with mobile phone assembly can buy new equipment, hire and pay employees, and expand into other regions.

The value of fiat money is dependent on how a country's economy is performing, how the country is governing itself, and the effects of these factors on interest rates. A country experiencing political instability is likely to have a weakened currency and inflated commodity prices, making it hard for people to buy products as they may need. A fiat currency functions well when the public has enough confidence in the currency's ability to act as a storage medium for purchasing power. Also, it must be backed by the full credit of the government that gives a decree and prints it as a legal tender for financial transactions.

Challenge & Advantages of Fiat Currency

The most important feature of fiat money is the stability of its value, unlike commodity-based money like gold, copper, and silver. The use of fiat money became popular in the 20th century as governments and banks moved in to protect their economies from the frequent busts of the business cycle.

Commodity-based currencies were volatile due to the regular business cycle and periodic recessions. The central banks can print or hold paper money as they may need, giving them greater control over the money supply, interest rates, and liquidity. For example, the Federal Reserve's control over the money supply and demand enabled it to manage the Global Financial Crisis of 2008 from causing greater harm to the U.S. financial system and global economy.

Although fiat money is viewed as a more stable currency that can cushion against recessions, the global financial crisis proved otherwise. Even though the Federal Reserve controls the money supply, it was not able to prevent the crisis from happening. Critics of fiat money argue that the limited supply of gold makes it a more stable currency than fiat money, which has an unlimited supply.

The most important concern of fiat money is the fact that it lacks the intrinsic value. As the fiat money is not related to intrinsic value of any goods or services, over a period of time, the currency system and value chain have started progressing in different paces. Inflation, black money and corruption are also related by products of fiat money. Ultimately nowadays citizens are more concerned about the money than the value associated with the same.

Unlike the traditional commodity-backed currencies, fiat currency cannot be converted or redeemed. It is intrinsically valueless and used by government decree. For a fiat currency to be successful, the government must protect it against counterfeiting and manage the money supply responsibly.

Digital currency is a form of currency that is available only in digital or electronic form. It is also called digital money, electronic money, electronic currency, or cyber cash. Digital currencies have utility similar to that of physical currencies. They can be used to purchase goods and pay for services. Digital currencies only exist in digital form. They do not have a physical equivalent. Digital currencies can be centralized or decentralized. Fiat currency, which exists in physical form, is a centralized system of production and distribution by a central bank and government agencies. Prominent crypto currencies, such as Bitcoin and Ethereum, are examples of decentralized digital currency systems. Digital currencies can transfer value. Use of digital currencies requires a mental shift in the existing framework for currencies, where they are associated with sale and purchase transactions for goods and services. Digital currencies, however, extend the concept of fiat currency in digital form.

Challenges & Advantages of Digital Currencies

The most prominent disadvantage is the lack of intrinsic value of the digital currency as is with the physical fiat currency system.

They have fast transfer and transaction times. Because digital currencies generally exist within the same network and accomplish transfers without intermediaries, the amount of time required for transfers involving digital currencies is extremely fast. As payments in digital currencies are made directly between the transacting parties without the need for any intermediaries, the transactions are usually instantaneous and low-cost. This fares better compared to traditional payment methods that involve banks or clearinghouses. Digital-currency-based electronic transactions also bring in the necessary record keeping and transparency in dealings.

They do not require physical manufacturing and cannot be soiled. Many requirements for physical currencies, such as the establishment of physical manufacturing facilities, are absent for digital currencies. Such currencies are also immune to physical defects or soiling that is present in physical currency.

They can ease implementation of monetary and fiscal policy. Under the current currency regime, the Fed works through a series of intermediaries—banks and financial institutions—to circulate money into an economy. CBDCs can help circumvent this mechanism and enable a government agency to disburse payments directly to citizens. They also simplify the production and distribution methods by obviating the need for physical manufacturing and transportation of currency notes from one location to another.

They can make transaction costs cheaper. Digital currencies enable direct interactions within a network. For example, a customer can pay a shopkeeper directly as long as they are situated in the same network. Even costs involving digital currency transactions between different networks are relatively cheaper as compared to those with physical or fiat currencies. By cutting out middlemen that seek economic rent from processing the transaction, digital currencies can make the overall cost of a transaction cheaper.

They do not solve all storage and infrastructure problems. While they do not require physical wallets, digital currencies have their own set of requirements for storage and processing. For example, an Internet connection is necessary as are smart phones and services related to their provisioning. Online wallets with robust security are also necessary to store digital currencies.

They are susceptible to hacking. Their digital provenance makes digital currencies susceptible to hacking. Hackers can steal digital currencies from online wallets or change the protocol for digital currencies, making them unusable. As the numerous cases of hacks in crypto currencies have proved, securing digital systems and currencies is a work-in-progress.

They can be volatile in value. Digital currencies used for trading can have wild price swings. For example, the decentralized nature of crypto currencies has resulted in a profusion of thinly capitalized digital currencies whose prices are prone to sudden changes based on investor whims. Other digital currencies have followed a similar price trajectory during their initial days. For example, Linden dollars used in the online game Second Life had a similarly volatile price trajectory in its early days.

III. DIGITAL VALUE SYSTEM

All these decades we were trying an external entity called currency/money to exchange the value of goods and services as there never existed a total scientific method to determine the value of each and every entity on this earth and moreover value was either context based or based on various other parameters. With the kind of inclusive development and progress human kind has achieved in digital technology and information systems, we are in a position now to think of an innovative method for determining and exchanging value. We propose a digital value system which is stemmed in the principle of intrinsic value system clubbed with the digital value exchange system.

We propose a one world model to value goods and services based on intrinsic value and various other parameters including cost of production index if any, supply & demand index, countries total economic index and a digital exchange system to enable trade and transactions of such derived values, enabling a standardized digital value system. In the proposed model we plan to derive an intrinsic value for each and every entity in this world on the basis of its chemical composition, availability index, essentiality index and usefulness index. We propose to derive the country's total economic index based on several parameters including land area, populations, sum total of intrinsic value of all resources present, GDP, education attitude and knowledge of human resources, happiness index etc. Once the intrinsic value and total economic index is derived, the absolute value of an entity or resource for a country or region can be calculated with the cost of production index and demand & supply index for a given period of time. It has to be noted that the total value of a country/ region will be equivalent to the sum total of intrinsic value of all the entities and resources of the country/ region and the intrinsic value of an entity can be transferred to another entity completely or partly in case of consumption and transformation of the same. The sum total of intrinsic value of all the entities of the world constitutes the total value of the world and thus defines the equilibrium of transfer of value between the entities.

A simulation scenario of the digital value system from the human way of thinking can be explained as below. Let's assume that all the entities on the earth have been given an intrinsic value using some formula and all needed parameters of value estimation and all humans by are given a base intrinsic value. This value is again updated based on the inheritance of values from parents. Now the new born child is having an intrinsic value x . The child grows consuming various resources like milk, food and it adds/subtracts to the intrinsic value of him. Going forward he acquires education, skills and all these have intrinsic values which gets added/subtracted to him based on his performance and his works. A minimum mandatory base value of reserve is maintained for all human beings for the basic needs of life on earth which is protected by law and hence humans will never be deprived of basic essential resources like food, water, air, clothing and shelter for their life on earth. Now the Digital Value System will keep stock of and maintain the registry of intrinsic value of each and every thing whenever it gets updated or transacted or changed. A person by his education, attitude, skills and work performed acquires further value for him to be utilized for exchange of goods and services.

The challenge to enable such a digital value system is the mandate to have a total digital connected world with an AI based Global Management Information System in place monitoring each and every aspect of life and transformations happening on earth. Establishment of various standard indexes like essentiality index, usefulness index, availability index, priority index, total national economic index, demand & supply index etc. A model/formula for intrinsic value derivation of each and every entity of the world need to be derived/fixed based on various parameters and the total world intrinsic value needs to be calculated. Model for reassignment and updating of intrinsic value of entities to be in place according to the change/transformation happening in life on earth as time progresses.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Concluding the chapter the implementation of the Digital Value System will avoid the use of an external agent like currency or money to exchange value and value as such is being carried by each and every entity in the world and exchanged or transferred between entities avoiding any intermediary through the AI based global management information system. Will result in better transparency and efficiency of exchange of value and will lead to better utilization of resources. Humans will realize and live for value creation instead of going behind the exchange medium which will eventually lead to equality, harmony in life and work, global awareness and planning, more systematic and scientific approach to value, better control and management for Governments to estimate their worth and potentials, will ease international exchange of value of goods and services with a one world view, will revolutionizes the present banking and finance systems, will lead to a new way of life and thinking for human beings.

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